

The Influence of Service Quality and Company Image on Customer Satisfaction of Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor

Daffa Amalia Putri^{1*}, Samsuri², Yulianingsih³
Juanda University, Bogor

Corresponding Author: Daffa Amalia Putri daffa.amalia2019@unida.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine and analyze the quality of service and corporate image either simultaneously or partially on customer satisfaction at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor. Sampling amounted to 100 respondents who were taken by probability sampling technique with simple random sampling method. The questionnaire was tested with validity test, reliability test, and also classical assumption test. The results of these tests are valid, reliable, and can be used for regression data. The analytical method used in this research is descriptive and verification method with a quantitative approach. The results of the study show that the variables of service quality and corporate image either simultaneously or partially have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor. The result of testing the coefficient of determination R (square) is 45.3%, while the rest is 54.7%. The relationship between service quality and corporate image is strong with a correlation coefficient of 0.682.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, the business world is experiencing very rapid growth, both businesses operating in the service sector and non-service sectors, including the automotive industry. Currently, the automotive industry is one of the leading industries in Indonesia, because the growth of the automotive world is increasing rapidly from year to year. This is supported by the situation where vehicles are no longer exclusive and luxurious like in the past, but have become normal things that are needed to support daily activities.

The city of Bogor is one of the areas that has a good level of economic growth and is developing rapidly, so this opportunity can be exploited by business people, especially in the automotive industry, by opening an official car sales dealer in the city of Bogor, including:

Table 1. Names of Official Car Dealers in Bogor City in 2022

No	Dealer Name	Car Brand
1	PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur	Mitsubishi
2	Astra Daihatsu Yasmin	Daihatsu
3	Honda	Honda
4	Daihatsu Bogor	Daihatsu
5	Astra International Tbk Daihatsu	Daihatsu
6	DFSK Bogor	DFSK
7	Suzuki Mobil Jabodetabek	Suzuki
8	Suzuki Tajur Bogor Citra Asri Buana	Suzuki
9	Honda Mandiri Bogor	Honda
10	Toyota Auto2000 Bogor	Toyota
11	Indomobil Nissan Datsun Bogor Padjajaran	Datsun
11	Wuling Bogor	Wuling
12	Setiajaya Toyota Pajajaran	Toyota

Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

Table 1. shows the names of official dealers in the city of Bogor, including Honda, Toyota, Wuling, Daihatsu, Datsun, Suzuki and Astra. The car dealer's business activities are car sales, car service, and spare parts sales with different service qualities.

The intense competition among car dealers encourages companies to look for the right strategy so that the company can win the competition. One strategy that can be implemented is through consumer satisfaction. According to Tjiptono (2016:74), consumer satisfaction is a person's feeling of happiness or disappointment that arises after comparing perceptions of the performance of a product and their expectations. According to Irawan (2015:37), it is stated that several factors influence consumer satisfaction, namely: 1) product quality; 2) price; 3) service quality; 4) emotional factors; and 5) cost and ease of obtaining products or services. The indicators of consumer satisfaction according to Tjiptono (2014: 101) are 1) conformity to expectations; 2) interest in visiting again; 3) willingness to recommend.

The first factor that influences consumer satisfaction is service quality. According to Lupiyoadi (2014: 216), service quality is how far the difference is

between reality and consumer expectations for the service received. Service quality can be measured through indicators; 1) direct (tangible) evidence; 2) reliability (reliability); 3) responsiveness (responsiveness); 4) guarantee (assurance); 5) empathy (empathy). Previous research conducted by Triyadi, et al (2021) stated that service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

Apart from service quality, a factor that is often associated with consumer satisfaction is company image. Each company has a different image, the company's weaknesses and advantages when faced with other companies will reveal the company's position compared to other companies. According to Kanaidi (2015:5), company image is the ability of a company to influence its perception of what is offered and will have an impact on consumer purchasing behavior. The company image indicators are; 1) A collection of impressions; 2) Beliefs; 3) Attitudes. Previous research conducted by Jayananda & Suarmanayasa I N (2022) stated that company image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. The following is the official workshop income data from PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur is known as the income of PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur in 2021 is quite volatile. So the achievement of the revenue target only reached 88%. Revenue realization that exceeded the target occurred in January, August and December. December was the month with the highest achievement with a percentage of 109%, this happened because consumers usually go to have their cars serviced in preparation for the long year-end holidays. In January the revenue percentage was 101%, this happened because consumers came back for service after completing the long holiday at the end and beginning of the year. In August the revenue percentage was 102%, because of PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur often holds special Independence Day discounts and other bonuses, so that consumers become interested in having their cars serviced at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur. Meanwhile, for other months, the failure to achieve the revenue target was caused by many factors, including the many choices of car repair shops as service locations and also the decline in consumer satisfaction which was thought to be caused by the quality of service and company image. According to Windarti (2017: 8), consumer satisfaction is a situation shown by consumers, when they realize that their needs and desires are as expected. The more expectations are met, the more satisfied consumers are.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Every effort is made by PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur provides excellent quality service to fulfill consumer needs and desires, as well as accuracy in delivery to match consumer expectations. To find out how to assess the quality of service at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur, conducted a preliminary survey by distributing questionnaires to 30 respondents who were consumers of PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur. This Preliminary Survey was conducted via Google Form for 5 days, namely 01-05 August 2022. The following are the results of the pre-survey regarding service quality, namely: regarding the quality of service to PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur in 2022.

Indicators that are considered less good are tangible, reliability, responsiveness and assurance, while the empathy indicator gets a good assessment from consumers. So, it can be concluded that the quality of service provided by PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur is considered by consumers to be not optimal in meeting consumer expectations.

METHODOLOGY

Object of Research

The object of this research is service quality, brand image and consumer satisfaction. The subjects of this research are consumers of PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur, the location of this research is PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur which is located at Jalan Raya Tajur No. 62 RT.001 RW.004 Pakuan, Bogor.

Research Design

This research used a verification research approach through data collection by observation (questionnaires or questionnaires) at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur.

Research Variable

1. Independent Variable (X), is an independent variable whose existence is not influenced by other variables. The independent variables in this research are service quality and company image.
2. Dependent Variable (Y), This is a variable whose existence is greatly influenced and depends on the independent variable. The dependent variable in this research is consumer satisfaction.

Population

A study certainly requires a population as a data source. The population is also called the universe, which means the whole which can be living or non-living objects. According to Silaen (2018:87), population is the totality of individuals or objects that have certain traits or characteristics that will be studied. The population in this study were workshop consumers at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur, numbering 1,606 based on workshop visit data in 2021.

Sample

According to Silaen (2018: 87), a sample is a portion of the population taken using a certain method to measure or observe its characteristics. So, in this study, the author determined the sample size using the Slovin formula according to Silaen (2014:91) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

The number of samples based on this calculation is 89 and rounded up to 100 respondents, namely consumers of PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Tajur.

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used in this research was a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Sugiyono (2018:82) states that proportionate stratified random sampling is used if the population has members or elements that are not homogeneous and proportionally stratified.

Data Types and Sources

1. **Primary Data:** Primary data is original data obtained and collected directly from the location by researchers. In this research, primary data was obtained by visiting the research location meeting respondents and conducting interviews, as well as by distributing questionnaires and observing (Silaen, 2018: 143).
2. **Secondary Data:** This is data obtained from the results of research by other parties, usually collected from the literature or previous researchers (Silaen, 2018: 143). The secondary data in this research was obtained through reading books, references in the library, literature or results of previous research, artifact journals and social media with trusted sources.

Method of Collecting Data

1. **Interview:** According to Sugiyono (2017:318), an interview is a meeting of two people who exchange information and ideas through questions and answers to gain meaning on a particular topic. An interview is a list of questions arranged systematically that will be asked directly to the object to be studied.
2. **Questionnaire:** Questionnaires are an important instrument in collecting research data, especially in collecting primary data. According to Sugiyono (2017:142), a questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving questions or written statements to selected respondents to answer.
3. **Observation:** Observasi dapat dilakukan dengan cara melihat langsung di lapangan misalnya kondisi ruang kerja dan lingkungan kerja yang bisa digunakan untuk menentukan faktor yang laying didukung dengan adanya wawancara dan kuesioner mengenai analisis jabatan. Menurut Sugiyono (2017:204) menyebutkan bahwa observasi sebagai teknik pengumpulan data yang memiliki ciri spesifik apabila dibandingkan dengan teknik lainnya.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

This analysis is used to find out how much influence the variables of service quality and company image have on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor. The results of calculating the regression coefficient of the influence of service quality and company image on consumer satisfaction can be seen in the regression test table using IBM SPSS 25 as follows:

Table 2. Multiple Linear Regression Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.773	2.352		754	.453		
Service quality	.345	.087	.420	.969	.000	.493	.028
Company Image	.301	.101	.315	.979	.004	.493	.028

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Satisfaction

Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 2, it is known that the regression equation with the estimated model is as follows:

$$Y = 1,773 + 0,345 X_1 + 0,301 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

This means that the regression coefficient is a number that shows the magnitude of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. Usually, the influence of each of these variables can be explained as follows:

1. A constant of 1.773 means that if the service quality and company image variables are constant or do not change then consumer satisfaction is positive.
2. The regression coefficient for service quality (X_1) = 0.345 is positive, meaning that if service quality is improved according to consumer expectations, it will be followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction (Y) assuming that other influencing variables remain constant or do not change.
3. The company image regression coefficient (X_2) = 0.301 is positive, meaning that if the company image is improved according to consumer expectations, this will be followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction (Y) assuming that other variables that influence consumer satisfaction remain the same or do not change.

Multiple Correlation Analysis

To see the correlation between variables, see the following table:

Table 3. Results of Multiple Correlation Calculation and Determination Coefficient

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.682 ^a	.464	.453	3.50473

a. Predictors: (constant) Company Image, Service Quality...

b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Satisfaction

Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 3 of the statistical calculations, it can be seen that the R-value or correlation is 0.682 which shows the correlation or relationship of the independent variables consisting of service quality (X1) and company image (X2) with the dependent variable, namely consumer satisfaction (Y) which has a strong correlation. (0.600 – 0.800) and positive (Sugiyono, 2019: 267). So, it can be concluded that the better the service quality (X1) and company image (X2), the positive influence it will have on consumer satisfaction at the PT workshop. Sun Star Prima Motor.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination (R Square)

Based on the table, the results obtained from R square are 0, 453 or 45.3%. This shows the percentage contribution of the variable influence of service quality and company image on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor was 45.3% while the remaining 54.7% was influenced by other variables not included in this research such as product quality, emotional factors, cost and convenience (Irawan, 2015:37).

Hypothesis testing

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

To test the statistical hypothesis, the F test statistic obtained through the analysis of variance (ANOVA) table is used as follows:

Table 4. Results of Simultaneous Regression Coefficient testing

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Significance
1	Regression	1033.285	2	516.642	42.061	.000 ^b
	Residual	1191.465	97	12.283		
	Total	2224.750	99			

- a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Satisfaction
 - b. Predictors: (constant) Company Image, Service Quality...
- Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 4., the F_{count} is 42.061, while the F_{table} needs to be calculated using the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ and degrees of freedom ($df = n - k$) or $100 - 2 - 1 = 97$. By looking at the results of the degrees of freedom, the F_{table} value is 3.090 so that $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($42.061 > 3.090$) and has a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that service quality (X1) and company image (X2) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor.

Partial Test (t Test)

Tabel 5. Hasil Uji T

Coefficients ^a		
Model	T	Sig.
(Constant)	.754	.453
Service quality	3.969	.000
Company Image	2.979	.007

Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Car Service Workshops at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor

To see whether or not there is an influence of service quality on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor, statistically the hypothesis will be tested as follows:

- $H_{01}: \beta_1 \leq 0$: Service quality does not have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor.
- $H_{a1}: \beta_1 > 0$: Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor.

Figure 1. T Test Results for Service Quality Variables (X1)
 Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

The Influence of Company Image on Customer Satisfaction in Car Service Workshops at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor

To see whether or not there is an influence of company image on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor, statistically the hypothesis was tested as follows:

- Ho2: $\beta_2 \leq 0$: Company image has no positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor.
- Ha2: $\beta_2 > 0$: Company image has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at the Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor.

Based on the table, it can be seen that the count for the corporate image variable (X2) of 2.757 is greater than the table value of 1.660 ($2.979 > 1.660$) and the significant value of 0.007 is smaller than 0.05 ($0.007 < 0.05$). So Ha2 is accepted and Ho2 is rejected, which means that partially the company image variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction (Y) Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor. This is by the research results of Bagus Subantoro and Aniek Wahyuati (2019) that there is a positive and significant influence of company image on consumer satisfaction. The results of other research by Lira Arlia Meilani (2019) show that there is a positive and significant influence of company image on consumer satisfaction. The one-party test for the company image variable can be seen in the following picture:

Figure 2. Corporate Image Variable T Test (X2)
 Source: Author Processed Data, 2022

From the test results, a partial test recapitulation was made, namely the service quality (X1) and company image (X2) variables as follows:

Table 6. Partial Test Recapitulation

No	Variabel	t_{hitung}	t_{tabel}	Conclusion
1	Service quality	3,969	1,660	Service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
2	Company Image	2,979	1,660	Company image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

Source Author Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the two independent variables, namely service quality (X1) and company image (X2), have a partially positive and significant effect on the dependent variable, namely consumer satisfaction (Y). This is shown by the count value of all these variables being greater than the table value. According to Maja and Sudibis (2012: 56), stated that to find out which independent variable has the dominant influence on the dependent variable, the Standardized Beta Coefficient is used. With this, the service quality variable (X1) is the dominant variable in its influence on consumer satisfaction (Y). This can be proven in Table 4.5 by the value of the Standardized Coefficient Beta for the service quality variable (X1), which is 0.420, where this value is the largest compared to the Standardized Coefficient Beta value for the corporate image variable (X2) of 0.315.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research and hypothesis testing that has been carried out regarding the influence of service quality and company image on customer satisfaction at car service workshops at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. Consumer assessment of service quality (X1) at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor is included in the good category. The highest value is in the tangible indicator, and the lowest is in the collateral indicator.
2. Consumer assessment of the company's image (X2) is included in the good category. The highest value is for the impression set indicator, and the lowest is for the trust indicator.
3. Consumer assessment of consumer satisfaction (Y) is included in the satisfied category. The highest value is for the impression set indicator, and the lowest is for the trust indicator.

Simultaneous test results show that service quality and company image simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at car service workshops at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor. Partial test results:

- a. Service quality influences customer satisfaction at car service workshops at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor positively and significantly.
- b. The company image influences customer satisfaction at the car service workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor positively and significantly.

The suggestions are given to the service department of PT. Sun Star Prima Motor includes the following:

- a. Consumer satisfaction (Y), the lowest instrument is that consumers will state positive things about PT. Sun Star Prima Motor. Employees should always try to fulfill consumer desires so that consumers are satisfied with the service provided so that consumers give positive assessments as a form of appreciation. Apart from that, the company also needs to improve the quality of services provided by PT workshops. Sun Star Prima Motor to make consumers feel satisfied so they will service their cars at the company.
- b. Quality of service (X1), the lowest instrument is a reliable mechanic. Companies need to improve the performance of employees, especially mechanics, in carrying out work so that consumers can feel satisfied with what is expected. That way, consumers will decide to carry out vehicle maintenance and repairs again at the PT workshop. Sun Star Prima Motor.
- c. Company image (X2), the lowest instrument is consistency in serving consumers. Companies should improve employee performance to increase consistency in providing service at PT workshops. Sun Star Prima Motor.
- d. Future researchers can use this research as reference and reference material. It would be better for researchers to look for other variables that can influence emotional factors, product factors, costs and convenience to obtain more perfect results.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Influence of Service Quality and Company Image on Customer Satisfaction of Car Service Workshop at PT. Sun Star Prima Motor Bogor".

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